

Words and concepts	Definition	Definition Source	Contributing partner
AR5 or 6	IPCC's Fifth/Sixth Assessment Report	https://www.ipcc.ch/	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
Adaptation	Adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities. Various types of adaptation can be distinguished, including anticipatory and reactive adaptation, private and public adaptation, and autonomous and planned adaptation	https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/03/wg2TARannexB.pdf	Enora Bruley, UNIGE
Capacity Building	The process by which individuals or organizations obtain, improve, or retain the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment, or other resources to do their work competently	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/adaptation-options/capacity-building-on-climate-change-adaptation	
Citizen engagement	Refers to the active participation of individuals and communities in governance processes, encompassing decision-making, implementation, and monitoring	https://www.interregeurope.eu/sites/default/files/2025-02/Policy%20brief%20on%20citizen%20engagement_0.pdf	
Citizen Science	partnerships between scientists and non-scientists in which authentic data are collected, shared, and analyzed	Jordan, RC, Ballard, HL, Phillips, TB. 2012. Key issues and new approaches for evaluating citizen-science learning outcomes. Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment 10: 307–309. DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.1890/110280.	Marianna Adinolfi, CMCC
Climate adaptation tools	Tools based on climate change projects for local areas, e.g., including potential climate impacts and suggested adaptation priorities. Such tools help stakeholders like decision makers, businesses, educators, scientists, communities and private persons to anticipate, plan for, and adapt to projected climatic changes	https://www.epa.gov/arc-x/tools-climate-change-adaptation	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
Climate Change	A long-term change in the average weather patterns that have come to define Earth's local, regional, and global climates	https://science.nasa.gov/climate-change/what-is-climate-change/	
Climate index	Climate indices are diagnostic tools used to describe the state of the climate system and monitor climate. They are most often represented with a time series, where each point in time corresponds to one index value. An index can be constructed to describe almost any atmospheric event.	https://cdiac.ess-dive.lbl.gov/climate/indices/indices_table.html	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
Climate projections	Projections of future climate conditions via complex climate models.	https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/paleoclimatology/climate-reconstruction	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
Climate reconstructions	Reconstruction of a previous climate at a specific date or time, usually via observations or paleoclimatic studies.	https://climate.copernicus.eu/climate-projections	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn

Climate risks	The potential for adverse consequences for human or ecological systems, recognising the diversity of values and objectives associated with such systems. In the context of climate change, risks can arise from potential impacts of climate change as well as human responses to climate change. Relevant adverse consequences include those on lives, livelihoods, health and well-being, economic, social and cultural assets and investments, infrastructure, services (including ecosystem services), ecosystems and species.	https://apps.ipcc.ch/glossary/	Marianna Adinolfi, CMCC
Climate services	"Relevant, credible, and accessible to users, acknowledges uncertainty, is communicated through a user-specific format, and is timely for user needs. It is developed by users and producers through tailored interaction, while building trust, and increasing users' capacity for using the service and understanding the issue at hand. The service delivers benefits to the user and supports better decision-making for adaptation" (Boon et al., 2024, p.5).	Boon, E., Meijering, J. V., Biesbroek, R., & Ludwig, F. (2024). Defining successful climate services for adaptation with experts. Environmental Science & Policy, 152, 103641.	Sukaina Bharwani, SEI Oxford
CMIP5 /CMIP6	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, Phase 5 or 6	https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmip	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
Co-assessment (WP4)	Collect citizen/stakeholders feedback on climate public services, governance or public outcomes, as well as on climate impacts	Loeffler, E., Bovaird, (eds.) (2021) The Palgrave Handbook of Co-production of Public Services and Outcomes, Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke, UK. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-53705-0_32	Anna S
Co-benefit (D3.2)	A positive effect that a policy or measure aimed at one objective has on another objective, thereby increasing the total benefit to society or the environment. Co-benefits are also referred to as ancillary benefits. (IPCC definitions - we may need to update to be relevant to us)	IPCC Glossary Search	Rosie Witton, SEI Oxford
Co-Creation	Collaboratively creating outputs like tools or policy recommendations. A process that can add value and increase innovative potential through intentional experience design	https://www.navarinoneo.se/knowledge-co-creation	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
		https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-10-8500-0_2	Rosie Witton, SEI Oxford
Co-defined (D3.2)	To articulate the implicit and explicit meaning of a particular term together with one or more people, in this case climate change adaptation strategies, policies or actions.	-	Mathilda Englund, SEI HQ

Co-design	To create ways in which challenges can be addressed together with one or more people, implementing different methodologies and/or approaches such as lateral thinking to propose innovative solutions to current pressing climate change related issues. It may also include devising effective, analytical-deliberative procedures/processes and sustainable problem-solving techniques and strategies directly applicable to the challenges that need to be addressed.	CO-DESIGN English meaning - Cambridge Dictionary	Rosie Witton, SEI Oxford
Co-develop	To determine the best manner to satisfy the requirements for an expected output together with one or more people or organizations. This includes analytical deliberative procedures for engagement of citizens/stakeholders related to the creation of adaptation projects and evaluating baseline requirements and consider all potential alternatives to solve a particular climate risk or impact challenge.	CO-DEVELOP English meaning - Cambridge Dictionary	Rosie Witton, SEI Oxford
Co-explore (D3.2)	Explore the perspectives of key actors within co-production processes to assess the challenges and opportunities faced, and describe this idea to capture the process through which boundaries might be actively subverted through sustained engagement between the origins of multiple, diverse perspectives.	Howarth, C., Lane, M., Morse-Jones, S., Brooks, K., & Viner, D. (2022). The 'co' in co-production of climate action: challenging boundaries within and between science, policy and practice. <i>Global Environmental Change</i>, 72, 102445.	Marta Ellena, CMCC
Co-evaluation	To validate potential solutions or partial solutions to a particular challenge or issue jointly with one or more people. This implies considering available information, processes and how adequate the solution is in meeting the needs and expectations of stakeholders.		Rosie Witton, SEI Oxford
Co-implementation (WP4)	Enlist citizens in ensuring that pathways to public climate adaptation outcomes are successfully implemented	Loeffler, E., Bovaird, (eds.) (2021) <i>The Palgrave Handbook of Co-production of Public Services and Outcomes</i>, Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke, UK. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-53705-0_32	Anna S
Co-management (D3.2)	Co-regulation and co-management give the right to participants to be directly included in designing, revising or reviewing regulations and risk management measures, rule-making processes or programmes for monitoring risks.	IRGC (2020). <i>Involving stakeholders in the risk governance process</i>. Lausanne: EPFL International Risk Governance Center. DOI: 10.5075/epfl-irgc-282243	Rosie Witton, SEI Oxford
Co-production	“Iterative and collaborative processes involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge and actors to produce context-specific knowledge and pathways towards a sustainable future” (Norström, et al., 2020:183).	Norström, A.V., Cvitanovic, C., Löf, M.F. et al. <i>Principles for knowledge co-production in sustainability research</i>. <i>Nat Sustain</i> 3, 182–190 (2020). https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0448-2	Sukaina Bharwani, SEI Oxford

Community Engagement	Input delivered by communities, e.g., local inhabitants have worked on the data or participatory methods have been included	https://mrsc.org/explore-topics/environment/sustainability/climate-equity-and-engagement	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
CORDEX	Coordinated Regional Downscaling Experiment: A Global Climate Model (GCM) can provide reliable prediction information on scales of around 1000 by 1000 km covering what could be a vastly differing landscape (from very mountainous to flat coastal plains for example) with greatly varying potential for floods, droughts or other extreme events. Regional Climate Models (RCM) and Empirical Statistical Downscaling (ESD), applied over a limited area and driven by GCMs can provide information on much smaller scales supporting more detailed impact and adaptation assessment and planning, which is vital in many vulnerable regions of the world.	https://cordex.org/about/what-is-regional-downscaling/	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
Cost Analysis	Breaking down costs, comparing against other scenarios, and or projecting future costs.	https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/cost-benefit-analysis	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
EURO-CORDEX	European branch of the international CORDEX initiative: In 2009 the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) established the Task Force for Regional Climate Downscaling (TFRC), which created the CORDEX initiative to generate regional climate change projections for all terrestrial regions of the globe within the timeline of the Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) and beyond.	https://www.euro-cordex.net/060374/index.php.en	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
GCM	Global Climate Model: Complex mathematical representation of the major climate system components (atmosphere, land surface, ocean, and sea ice), and their interactions. Earth's energy balance between the four components is the key to long-term climate prediction.	https://www.gfdl.noaa.gov/climate-modeling/	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
Impact	Assessing the effects of climate change towards a pre-defined spatial scale	https://www.noaa.gov/education/resource-collections/climate/climate-change-impacts	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
Interscalability	Criteria to decide of tools can be used outside of their own scale (e.g. Regional tool can be used locally). The reference refers to scaling-up, but interscalability refers to the ability to scale up and down the tools output to suit the users needs.	https://mispgh.unimelb.edu.au/centres-institutes/nossal-institute-for-global-health/implementation-science/how/step-4-scaling	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change: the United Nations body for assessing the science related to climate change.	https://www.ipcc.ch/	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
Policy Frameworks	Used to adopt policies in a coherent and effective way. They provide an overarching strategy (including a methodology) of how to tackle an issue or policy-dependent situation.	https://www.bath.ac.uk/corporate-information/policy-framework/	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
Public Awareness	A process that seeks to inform and educate people about a topic or issue with the intention of influencing their attitudes,	SDG Accountability Handbook.	

	behaviours and beliefs towards the achievement of a defined purpose or goal.		
RCM	Regional Climate Model: Numerical climate prediction model forced by specified lateral and ocean conditions from a general circulation model (GCM) or observation-based dataset (reanalysis) that simulates atmospheric and land surface processes, while accounting for high-resolution topographical data, land-sea contrasts, surface characteristics, and other components of the Earth-system.	https://glossary.ametsoc.org/wiki/Regional_climate_model	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway: Greenhouse gas concentration trajectory adopted by the IPCC. Four RCPs produced from Integrated Assessment Models were selected from the published literature and are used in the Fifth IPCC Assessment Report as a basis for the climate predictions and projections presented in WGI AR5 Chapters 11 to 14.	https://ar5-syr.ipcc.ch/topic_summary.php	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
RCP 2.6	One pathway where radiative forcing peaks at approximately 3 W m ⁻² before 2100 and then declines (the corresponding ECP assuming constant emissions after 2100)	https://www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/glossary/glossary_r.html	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
RCP 4.5 & RCP 6.0	Two intermediate stabilisation pathways in which radiative forcing is stabilised at approximately 4.5 W m ⁻² and 6.0 W m ⁻² after 2100 (the corresponding ECPs assuming constant concentrations after 2150)	https://www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/glossary/glossary_r.html	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
RCP 8.5	One high pathway for which radiative forcing reaches greater than 8.5 W m ⁻² by 2100 and continues to rise for some amount of time (the corresponding ECP assuming constant emissions after 2100 and constant concentrations after 2250).	https://www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/glossary/glossary_r.html	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
Resilience	Communities' ability to withstand hazards from climate change; higher resilience means communities can withstand greater hazards without quality of life dropping. Related tools may provide measures to improve this ability.	CC2ES Climate Resilience Portal	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
Risk	Assessing likelihood to be subject to a certain hazard, incl. projecting future damages given no policy or no mitigation efforts (to showcase a worst-best case scenario)	Understanding climate risk: Why it matters for your organisation's resilience and performance	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
SRES	Special Report on Emission Scenarios: Comparable to baseline Emission Scenarios; following how emissions are regulated by different policy Scenarios; used in previous IPCC Assessment Reports (AR4 and earlier)	https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/03/sres-en.pdf	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
SSPs	Shared Socioeconomic Pathways: Examine how global society, demographics and economics might change over the next century and are now being used as important inputs for the latest climate models, feeding into the Sixth IPCC Assessment Report	https://www.carbonbrief.org/explainer-how-shared-socioeconomic-pathways-explore-future-climate-change	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn

Tipping Points	Concept showing scenarios where climate cannot recover to original levels. A common example is Sea-Ice loss: past a certain point, certain regions will not be able to recover their sea-ice extent or concentration; this principle can be applied e to a plethora of climatic variables like temperature, biodiversity loss, precipitation, sea-level rise.	https://www.studysmarter.co.uk/explanations/environmental-science/sustainability/tipping-points/	Andreas Hoy, SEI Tallinn
WMO	World Meteorological Organization	https://wmo.int/	Marianna Adinolfi, CMCC
Vulnerable communities	Vulnerability here can be defined as “the characteristics and circumstances of a community, system or asset that make it susceptible to the damaging effects of a (climate) hazard”	UNISDR, Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030, 2015.	Marta Ellena, CMCC
Multiethnic groups	Including or involving people of several different ethnicities (= groups of people with a shared culture, tradition, language, history, etc.)	https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/multiethnic	Marta Ellena, CMCC
Media literacy	Media literacy includes all the technical, cognitive, social, civic and creative capacities that allow a citizen to access, have a critical understanding of the media and interact with it. It refers to all kind of media (television, radio, press), through all kind of channels (traditional, internet, social media) and to all ages. A key stone in all possible definitions of media literacy is the development of critical thinking by the user.	https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=2541	Spyridoula Markou, ATC
Climate change disinformation	Climate disinformation is the intentional dissemination of false information related to climate change and climate action. It can take many forms, from hard denial and conspiracy theories to softer, more insidious disinformation that seeks to muddy the waters by claiming that climate change is not man-made or as bad as scientists are saying and therefore requires no urgent action.	https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/climate-disinformation_en	Spyridoula Markou, ATC
Fact-checking	Use of an evidence-based method to verify the accuracy of claims made in the public sphere.	https://efcsn.com/code-of-standards/	Spyridoula Markou, ATC
Disinformation	Disinformation is understood as verifiably false or misleading information that is created, presented and disseminated for economic gain or to intentionally deceive the public, and may cause public harm. Public harm comprises threats to democratic political and policy making processes as well as public goods such as the protection of EU citizens' health, the environment or security.	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52018DC0236	Spyridoula Markou, ATC
EUCRA	European Climate Risk Assessment	https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/european-climate-risk-assessment	Spyridoula Markou, ATC
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration	https://www.nasa.gov/	Spyridoula Markou, ATC
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration	https://www.noaa.gov/	Spyridoula Markou, ATC

